

BENEFITS OF BLACK SOLDIER FLY LARVAE IN ANIMALS – A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for animal protein has stimulated the development of insects as alternative proteins in animal feed. Insects show potential to replace fishmeal (FM) and soybean meal, especially in animal feed and aquaculture. Chickens and pigs need high protein content for good growth. Among the insect species as alternative protein sources is the black soldier fly (BSF), (*Hermetia illucens* L.). The black soldier fly larvae (BSFL) have the ability to convert organic waste into high-quality protein. Although BSFL contain high levels of protein, studies have shown that they can only partially replace feed due to their high fat content. Adding BSFL instead of FM to feed has a beneficial effect on growth and meat quality in poultry and pigs. FM can be successfully replaced with meal from BSFL without causing adverse effects on fish. This review aimed to demonstrate the benefits of partially including BSFL in animal feed intended for poultry, pigs and fish.

Key words: BSFL, poultry, pigs, fish.

Introduction

Animal feed is important for ensuring immunity, improved growth, and good health. Nowadays animal feed acts as protein source for livestock, poultry farming, and fish. Important protein constituents for feeding are soybean and FM and as well as animal proteins (Veldkamp *et al.*, 2012).

In some parts of the world, insects have been recognized as a potential source of raw materials.

Regarding the amino acid profile and nutritional composition, insects satisfy the dietary needs of animals (Schivavone *et al.*, 2018). Among insect species, BSF has several major advantages. The species is polyphagous, and its gut extracts have high amylase, lipase, and protease activities (Kim *et al.*, 2011).

As nature's recyclers, BSFL grown on organic waste, such as food scraps or agricultural by-products, converting them into high-value nutrients. This process not only minimizes waste but also provides a sustainable source of protein and essential fatty acids.

Veldkamp *et al.* (2012) found that the BSF and yellow meal worm (*T. molitor*) have a great potential for large-scale production of proteins of organic waste.

The insects are naturally found in the diets of some animals (such as poultry, pigs and fish). Poultry and pigs require high levels of protein for growth.

BSFL offers promising nutritional profiles as alternative protein sources for farm animals (Matsakidou *et al.*, 2024). BSFL are extensively studied and widely recognized for their balanced nutrient composition and potential for use in animal nutrition (Ewald *et al.*, 2020).

In addition to benefits, BSFL possesses nutritional advantages. They are rich in amino acids, fats, and micronutrients that are essential for the growth and health of animals, including poultry, aquaculture species, and pigs. By integrating larvae into feed, it can ensure a balanced diet for

animals while reducing reliance on limited resources. As a result, BSFL can be used as a feed additive for some farm animals. This review highlights the benefits of BSFL for poultry and pig feed, including improvements in growth and meat quality.

BSFL in poultry feed

Poultry farming is a rapidly growing sector that is of great importance for the nutrition of the population. Due to consumption in the broiler industry, several million tons of soybeans and corn are imported annually. Imports are mainly from Brazil and Argentina. The prices of these raw materials further affect the chicken industry and the price of chicken products (Abdurofi *et al.*, 2017).

Therefore, alternative approaches such as insect farming have been explored to reduce the cost of producing bird feed.

Insects play an important role in animal husbandry. They are an alternative protein option. Some insect species can be used as food sources for animals (Song *et al.*, 2018). This is because they are rich in proteins, vitamins, and amino acids which are necessary for animals. Given this nutritional value, insects are recommended as the most promising ingredients for animal feed (Van Huis, 2020). In confirmation of this, insects can replace traditional sources of protein such as FM and soybeans in poultry feed (Stamer, 2015).

In this regard, BSF and mealworm, given their high protein and fat content, are recommended as the most promising ingredients for animal feed (Van Huis, 2020).

It is important to note that while the larvae feed on waste and manure they produce 40% protein and 30% fat.

Nutritional composition of BSFL varied with age, where the protein content decreasing and fat content increasing as larvae matured (Aneibo and Owen, 2010).

In fact, the first poultry species to be fed feed containing 50% BSFL were quails (Widjastuti *et al.*, 2014).

Recent studies have investigated the effects of replacing conventional flours with BSFL, providing insight into meat and eggs characteristics (Schiavone *et al.*, 2019).

When included 15% BSF in broiler chicken feed and observed no negative impact on either their growth or meat quality (Uushona, 2015).

4% to 12% BSFL in the feed is the optimal percentage for improving broiler performance. Therefore, BSFL content in the feed of 5-15% can reduce feed costs as well as help with bird health (Zaid *et al.*, 2023).

Popova *et al.* (2020) found that the inclusion of 5% full-fat or partially defatted meal obtained from the BSFL in the diet of 35-day-old broilers had an impact on the quality characteristics of the meat, particularly in regard to fatty acid profile. The author reported significant increase of n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, and decrease in the n-6/n-3 ratio. In another study, Popova *et al.* (2021) found improved performance of the broilers at the age of 21 and 35 days when fed 5% full-fat or partially defatted BSF meal. The carcass weight and dressing percentage were higher in the groups receiving the insect meals. Overall, the study indicated good potential of the full fat and partially defatted BSF meal to positively alter the carcass composition of the broilers.

Similarly, Mlaga *et al.* (2020) observed an increase in meat protein levels and breast muscle yield in broilers compared to the control when BSFL was a replacement for FM in the feed.

According to Secci *et al.* (2020), when brown hy-line laying hens were fed a diet in which soybean meal was replaced with 25% defatted BSFL meal, they showed better egg quality parameters compared to the control group.

On the other hand, Mwaniki *et al.* (2020) completely replaced soybean meal with defatted BSF larval meal in white shaver hens and observed changes in body weight gain, eggshell thickness and yolk color compared to the control group.

In other poultry species, such as turkeys, Lalev *et al.* (2020) found that when soybean meal was replaced with BSF meal, effects were observed on growth and health parameters of turkey carcass meat. The results showed a better physiological response and immune status compared to the control group.

BSFL in pig feed

Due to the increasing world population, the demand for meat products is increasing. In addition to poultry, the consumption of pork is also increasing. Attention is being paid to the use of insects as animal feed (Van Raamsdonk *et al.*, 2017).

Since BSF has a rich nutritional value (Heuel *et al.*, 2021) it is used in animal husbandry and poultry farming.

Meanwhile, the use of BSF in the diet of fattening pigs has been studied. It is important to note that the specific nutritional properties of soldier fly larvae have an impact on animal health and even control the intestinal microbiota (Yu *et al.*, 2020).

It has recently been found that the addition of BSFL to pig fattening diets increases intramuscular fat content. There is still a lack of information on how BSFL affect muscle fiber differentiation and metabolism in growing pigs.

Zhu *et al.* (2022) show that replacing FM with 4% BSFL in the diet of growing pigs can significantly improve meat quality, and the addition of 8% black soldier fly has a beneficial effect on pig growth.

Replacing soybean meal with BSFL meal in the diet of growing pigs leads to beneficial changes in the microbiota and digestive metabolites. While in finishing pigs, replacing soybean meal with BSFL meal in the diet regulates the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines (Yu *et al.*, 2019).

Chia *et al.*, (2021) found that pigs fed FM diets completely replaced with BSFL meal had a high live body weight of 121 kg at fasting, while pigs fed a diet without BSFL meal had a low live body weight of 98 kg at slaughter. They believe that replacing FM with BSFL meal in pig feed leads to faster weight gain. These pigs reach market weight faster compared to pigs fed control diets. Furthermore, pigs fed diets containing BSFL meal had heavier carcasses than those fed a control diet based on FM. Therefore, BSFL meal is a suitable alternative to FM for pig feed in the international market. Pigs fed BSFL meal in the diet showed a combination of growth, carcass traits and nutritional quality of meat.

BSFL are characterized by being rich in fat, protein, and calcium and have a suitable amino acid profile for pigs. During weaning, piglets experience physical and nutritional stress. In pig farms, piglets are often weaned at around 3–4 weeks of age. This results in reduced feed intake after weaning. Reduced feed intake reduces gut growth and increases susceptibility to disease. However, BSFL are attractive to pigs and their inclusion in the diet has been shown to reduce stress in weaned piglets and promote feed intake (Ipema *et al.*, 2021). Pigs are naturally omnivorous animals with the ability to perform well on a variety of feeds.

Insect products (BSF, yellow mealworm, house fly, etc.) show great potential as an alternative source of protein in pig diets. Many studies have been conducted to evaluate the nutritional value of insect products to replace FM in weaned pig diets.

There is a need to investigate the optimal level of inclusion of insect products at each stage of pig growth in terms of productivity, quality and safety of pork (Hong and Kim, 2022).

Chia *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that BSFL meal can replace FM in pig feeds. They found that final body weight, fasting weight and carcass weight were significantly higher in the 50% and 100% supplement groups than in the 25% supplement and no supplement groups.

These results are important information to address the increasing shortage of protein-rich feeds.

BSFL has great potential as a source of protein in diets for poultry and pigs. It can replace soybean or FM as a source of feed protein.

BSFL in fish feed

Due to the increasing cost of FM on the market, it is necessary to look for an alternative source of protein for feed.

It has been found that BSFL meal can replace FM up to 50% in fish feed without any adverse effects (Stamer *et al.*, 2014). Thus, the use of BSFL meal can reduce aquaculture production costs without reducing fish quality. Aquaculture is threatened by the high cost of fish feed and the over-reliance on FM as the main source of protein. The goal in aquaculture is to minimize feed costs without significant side effects.

The demand for FM and soybean meal in aquaculture feeds is increasing and in this regard alternative protein carriers are attracting increasing interest. Replacing FM with insect meal also has potential in organic aquaculture feeds. These products will contribute to reducing the dependence on FM, cornmeal and soybean meal. BSF is an ideal candidate for this purpose. Larvae produce biomass with a protein content of about 42% and a fat content of up to 35% meal from BSFL as a source of protein in feed has been demonstrated in some warm-water fish species. However, studies on turbot and trout are limited (Kroeckel *et al.* 2012).

In aquaculture, BSFL has been found to replace FM in the diets of Pacific white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) by up to 25% (Cummins *et al.*, 2017), yellow catfish (*Pelteobagrus fulvidraco*) by up to 48% (Xiao *et al.*, 2018), juvenile barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) and Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) by up to 50% (Muin *et al.*, 2017).

In another study conducted with warm-water fish, Aisyah *et al.* (2022) included BSFL in the diet of tilapia from 10% to 30% and found that fish growth was not impaired.

Stammer *et al.* (2014) replaced FM with BSFL meal in rainbow trout at different replacement levels (0, 50, 75%). Growth and body weight gain were found to be affected by the BSFL meal content in the diet. No nutritional deficiencies and higher mortality were observed, so BSFL meal can replace FM up to 50% in trout feeds.

Studies show that the prospects for BSFL as a protein substitute for corn and soybean meal are promising. Due to their nutritional value, BSFL have the potential to provide quality protein in fish diets, leading to increased growth and production rates (Nairuti *et al.*, 2021).

One of the most economically farmed fish in the world is the Nile tilapia. In its cultivation, FM is replaced with BSFL in different percentage concentrations.

When including 75% BSFL meal in the diet of young Nile tilapia, growth is improved and there is no harmful effect on the liver and intestines. In addition, feed costs are reduced by 30%, resulting in 4% higher economic return (Limbu *et al.*, 2022).

The other fish species in which the replacement of FM with BSFL meal was studied were Koi carp (*Cyprinus carpio var. koi*). The study included 300 fish divided into five groups: a control

group and four experimental groups in which FM was replaced with 50, 100, 150 and 200 g kg⁻¹ BSFL. Fish fed 200 g kg⁻¹ BSFL meal showed significant weight gain compared to the control after 4 weeks, and this difference was maintained up to 8 weeks. This indicates that FM can be effectively replaced with BSFL meal (Linh, 2024).

Young Jian carp (*Cyprinus carpio var. Jian*) when fed with defatted BSFL meal up to 50% of the FM in their diet showed good growth, antioxidant enzyme activity and digestive enzymes. (Li *et al.*, 2017).

When FM was replaced by 64% defatted BSFL meal, young Japanese sea bass (*Lateolabrax japonicus*) showed good growth, good intestinal antioxidant activity, and better immune response (Guoxia *et al.*, 2019).

Replacing FM with up to 50% BSF pupae in the diet of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) has been shown to improve growth (Sealey *et al.*, 2011).

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) have also shown good growth response and feed conversion when fed BSFL meal (Belghit *et al.*, 2019).

When 50% FM is replaced with BSFL meal in the diet of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), positive effects on growth and feed utilization parameters have been observed (Muin *et al.*, 2017).

It should be noted that BSFL meal also has a positive impact on the species Pacific white shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*). When BSFL meal between 29% and 15% is present in the diet of Pacific white shrimp, it has been found that maximum protein content can be achieved (Cummins *et al.*, 2017).

The inclusion of insect meal in the diets of sturgeon acts as a growth stimulant. It is noteworthy that sturgeons may respond much better than other fish to this group of nutrients. Insect foods may be promising alternative food sources for Siberian sturgeon (Rawski *et al.*, 2020).

In addition to fish and shellfish, BSFL meal can also be used for ornamental fish farming, where it can replace fish meal up to 25-50% (Sanjaya *et al.*, 2020).

Conclusion

This study gives information about the possibilities to address the growing shortage of protein feed. The investigations have shown that BSFL can serve as a useful feed additive in poultry and pig feeds. The cited studies show that the inclusion of BSFL can effectively replace soybean and FM in the feed formulations. This substitution has benefits related to improved growth of chickens and pigs, improved meat quality and immunity in these animals.

In addition, BSFL can replace FM in fish feeds. It has been found that BSFL as a feed is beneficial for both food fish and ornamental fish.

Studies show that BSFL meal has promising prospects as a protein substitute for FM and soybean meal in the coming decades.

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